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OPTIMAL PRODUCT AND ASSORTMENT POLICY OF THE ENTERPRISE DURING THE PERIOD OF MARTIAL STATUS

ОПТИМАЛЬНА ТОВАРНА ТА АСОРТИМЕНТНА ПОЛІТИКА ПІДПРИЄМСТВА В ПЕРІОД ВІЙСЬКОВОГО СТАНУ

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Круглікова В.В., Кулабнієва О.А., Магдалина Ю.С. Оптимальна товарна та асортиментна політика підприємства в період військового стану. Оглядова стаття.

У статті досліджено підходи до оптимізації товарної та асортиментної політики підприємств в умовах воєнного стану. Визначено зміст і відмінності між товарною та асортиментною політикою, їхню роль у контексті змін кон'юнктури ринку. Розглянуто етапи формування маркетингової політики з урахуванням життєвого циклу товару, методи управління запасами, ресурсоощадження та адаптації до змін попиту. Підкреслено важливість гнучкості, інновацій та прогнозування споживчих тенденцій. Запропоновано рекомендації для забезпечення конкурентоспроможності підприємств у кризових умовах.

Ключові слова: товарна політика, асортиментна політика, військовий стан, управління запасами, маркетингові стратегії, конкурентоспроможність підприємства

Kruglikova V.V., Kulabnieva O.A., Magdalyn Yu.S. Optimal Product and Assortment Policy of the Enterprise During the Period of Martial Status. Review article.

The article examines approaches to optimizing the product and assortment policy of enterprises under martial law. The content and differences between product and assortment policy are determined, as well as their role in the context of changes in the market situation. The stages of forming a marketing policy taking into account the product life cycle, methods of inventory management, resource saving and adaptation to changes in demand are considered. The importance of flexibility, innovation and forecasting consumer trends is emphasized. Recommendations are proposed to ensure the competitiveness of enterprises in crisis conditions.

Keywords: product policy, assortment policy, martial law, inventory management, marketing strategies, enterprise competitiveness

A thorough analysis and development of marketing strategies can be a key success factor for Ukrainian retail enterprises in ensuring sustainable development and competitiveness in the market. The study of optimal marketing product policy in retail enterprises in Ukraine becomes particularly relevant during martial law in the context of rapid market transformation and changes in consumer habits.

Despite the large volume of research in the field of marketing, at present, not all aspects of the commodity policy of trading enterprises have been fully disclosed. Decision-making on commodity policy is carried out by enterprises without proper theoretical and practical justification. The development and scientific substantiation of commodity policy concepts is critically important for enterprises. Thus, research in this area requires urgent study.

Analysis of recent research and publications

The most important aspects of the formation of the enterprise's product policy have been studied in numerous works by the following domestic scientists: Pokropivny S.F., Kubyshina N.S., Kuchina S.E., Ilyashenko S.M., Orlov P.A., Kosenkov S.I., Prokhorova T.P., Osnach O.F., etc. The founders of the development of product policy are world-famous: Philip Kotler, Kevin Lane Keller, etc.

The aim of the article is to develop effective commodity and assortment policies of the enterprise in martial law. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set: to compare the definitions of commodity policy and assortment policy in order to identify their features and develop recommendations for their

harmonious combination, to develop methods for optimizing inventories and managing resources to ensure the stability of the enterprise in crisis conditions, to investigate methods for assessing the competitiveness of a trading enterprise, including the analysis of market positions and the development of strategies for increasing the competitiveness of the product offer, to develop methods for analyzing and planning control of commodity policy, including the use of modern technologies. Achieving the tasks set will allow forming a comprehensive and effective commodity and assortment policy of the enterprise, which takes into account the specific conditions of martial law and ensures the stability and competitiveness of the business.

The main part

It is known that the main tools in marketing are the so-called 4 "P" or marketing mix – this is Product

(goods), Price (price), Place (place, sales, distribution), Promotion (promotion, communication). In our case, the marketing mix (4 "P") is a set of marketing tools – a certain structure of the product range of trading enterprises, their pricing policy, promotion of goods and communication tools that ensure the achievement of the set goal and the solution of marketing tasks in the target market. However, the most important tool for marketing and competition is the product. It becomes the core of marketing, its price and communication are based on its features.

It is worth noting that the concepts of the enterprise's product policy and product range are not identical. The optimal product range is part of the enterprise's general product policy. The definitions of these concepts given by scientists are given in the form of a table (Table 1).

Table 1. Determining the product policy and product range of the enterprise

Author	Defining product policy	Definition of assortment policy
N.S. Kubyshina	A set of strategies and tactical measures aimed at satisfying consumer needs through an optimal range of products, maintaining product competitiveness, and ensuring sustainable development of the enterprise.	A set of measures aimed at creating and maintaining a product range that best meets the needs and expectations of consumers. It includes managing the product life cycle, introducing new products, and removing obsolete ones.
S.E. Kuchina	A set of management solutions aimed at creating, developing and managing a product range in order to maximize customer satisfaction and achieve high efficiency of the enterprise. It includes market analysis, innovation and range optimization.	A set of management decisions aimed at forming and optimizing the company's product range to maximize customer satisfaction and increase the competitiveness of products on the market.
S.M. Ilyashenko	A set of measures and strategies aimed at creating and managing a competitive product range, meeting consumer needs, and achieving the company's goals	A set of strategic and tactical measures aimed at managing the breadth and depth of the product range, ensuring their compliance with market requirements and achieving the company's goals
P.A. Orlov	A system of management decisions and actions aimed at forming and maintaining a product range that meets market needs and provides competitive advantages for the enterprise	A system of measures for managing the assortment of goods, which includes planning new products, modernizing existing ones, and removing those that have lost their relevance from the assortment. The purpose of the assortment policy is to meet the needs of consumers and increase the competitiveness of the enterprise
S.I. Kosenkov	A set of measures aimed at developing, implementing and managing a product range that allows an enterprise to meet consumer needs and maintain its competitiveness in the market	A set of management decisions and actions aimed at forming and optimizing the company's product range in order to meet consumer needs, maintain competitiveness, and ensure the stable development of the company.
T.P. Prokhorova	A set of strategic and tactical measures aimed at forming an optimal range of products, their development and management, which allows the enterprise to effectively respond to changes in market conditions and consumer needs.	A set of strategic and tactical measures aimed at forming, developing and managing the product range of an enterprise. This includes the introduction of new products, modification of existing ones and removal of obsolete products from the range to effectively meet consumer needs and achieve enterprise goals.
Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller	A set of management solutions aimed at creating and maintaining a competitive product range that satisfies consumer needs and allows the company to achieve its strategic goals. It includes product range planning, product lifecycle management, branding, and innovation.	The process of managing the breadth and depth of a company's product range to meet diverse customer needs and maintain competitiveness in the marketplace. This includes planning new products, eliminating obsolete products, and optimizing the range in response to changing market conditions.

Source: the authors' own elaboration

Since marketing product policy is considered a set of measures within the framework of which one or more products are selected as the main tools for achieving the goals of the enterprise, in our case of martial law, product policy is a very complex and diverse field of activity that requires making decisions regarding certain features of the product range during martial law, the optimal product range, the use of certain brand names, and packaging [7].

In the classification by scope, the following goods are distinguished:

- simple assortment, which are classified by a small number of characteristics; – complex assortment, which are represented by a significant number of groups, types, varieties and names that satisfy various needs for goods;
- branded assortment, which is a set of goods of the same group, but of different brands;
- a wide range, which is a set of goods that includes subgroups, types, varieties that belong to the same group, but differ from each other in individual characteristics;
- related assortment, which is a set of goods that perform auxiliary functions and do not belong to this group of goods;
- mixed assortment, which is a set of goods from different groups.

Trading enterprises make the following decisions within the framework of product policy:

- Implementation of a new product (analysis, product selection, implementation strategy, development of marketing materials);

- Product range (width, depth, completeness, degree of renewal, ratio, assortment structure);
- Product range (width, depth, richness, harmony);
- Information policy (identifying consumer preferences for goods and services, informing buyers about the product and organization, collecting market information);
- Pricing strategy (profit maximization, increasing sales volumes, gaining a larger market share, etc.).

When forming an effective product policy during military operations in a trading enterprise, it is worth paying attention to the special aspects of this type of organization:

1. The updating of goods in the trading process is more dynamic;
2. Assortment policy is related to the specialization of the company;
3. Attention should be paid to the optimal ratio of the permanent part of the assortment to the additional one;
4. Marketers of trading enterprises are tasked with continuously studying the behavior and demand of buyers and transmitting information to the manufacturer;
5. Trading enterprises often perform, in addition to their main function, also a production function related to the transportation and storage of products [1].

The principles of product policy are based on ensuring a balance between two opposing sides, the benefits of products for consumers and the competitiveness of the product range for the retailer. The main directions of marketing product policy as a whole are presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Structure of marketing product policy
Source: compiled by authors on materials [11]

The formation of a product policy can be carried out by various methods, depending on the scale of sales, issues related to logistics, the optimal assortment, the specifics of the organization, the goals

and objectives that the organization sets for itself. Having studied the existing works of scientists, a model of the formation of a product policy in a trading enterprise was supplemented and formed (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Model of formation and implementation of product policy at the enterprise
Source: the authors' own elaboration

Formation and management of assortment policy of trading companies includes implementation of a number of measures related to military changes of the logistics map in Ukraine, establishment of the optimal

assortment of products, development of new types of products, withdrawal of obsolete goods (elimination), organization of service, etc. Successful management of the product assortment is reflected in a dynamic set of

nomenclature positions that are in demand in the market. Thus, the interests of the company are expanded to the implementation of a product policy, which includes comprehensive market research (analysis of the competitiveness of the enterprise, conducting marketing research, studying consumer preferences, analysis of demand, etc.).

The process of managing the product range of an enterprise is based on the product life cycle. According to Philip Kotler, the product life cycle is a concept that describes the stages through which a product passes from the moment it enters the market until it is withdrawn from sale. Different products have different life cycles: from several days to dozens of years. The product life cycle consists of stages, each of which requires the enterprise to have an appropriate strategy and tactics of market behavior [8].

In February 2024, the research company Kantar studied the categories of grocery stores/daily goods to determine their uniqueness and show by example how Ukrainians choose brands.

As for the price factor, According to the survey, currently 52% of Ukrainian consumers are forced to limit themselves in consuming goods and services, as the financial status of Ukrainians has noticeably deteriorated over the past two years.

During martial law, buyers are forced to save on goods that bring pleasure. On goods for recreation, sports, beauty, hobbies. Ukrainians are forced to change their habits and are increasingly paying attention to goods at special prices, promotions, and turning to discount stores.

Marketers noted that over the past three years, consumers in Ukraine have tended to buy more products at special prices and on promotions: 57% now versus 31% in 2021. In addition, 35% now versus 21% in 2021 try to buy in economy class stores. As for the volume of purchases, the reasons have changed almost in the following proportions. 30% of buyers are trying to replace goods with cheaper analogues (in 2021 there were 11%).

Although price is known to be the most important factor in choosing, consumers still make choices among brands they know based on their personal attitude towards them over a long period of time. For example, in the hygiene products category, only 25% are guided by price, 60% by tradition, and 15% have retained a loyal attitude towards their brands.

As for pharmaceutical products, almost 57% choose according to tradition, 29% are guided by price, and only 14% of consumers have confidence in brands. It can be noted that price is an important, but not the key criterion.

In 2023, there was a rise in mainstream brands (cheaper brands). This was due to the fact that the demand for quality brands decreased sharply. This suggests that the importance of price is increasing. However, in 2023 we see the return of quality brands again.

It should be noted that iconic brands and star brands, as in the past, remained in their positions.

Kantar distinguishes several types of choices made by a person:

Type 1 (sometimes called System 1) is a fast brain that drives most of these decisions through emotions and intuition.

Type 2 consciously rationalizes the decisions of type 1, but is slow and resource-intensive [12].

Of course, strong brands are those that the consumer is drawn to. These brands directly influence the consumer, although he does not even realize it. At this level, emotion is "always on", because fast brain processes of type 1 are involved. They are the leaders of strong brands. In order to provoke a type 1 reaction, marketers identify the most significant difference between brands on the emotional level.

Kantar marketers have identified that an important feature of strong brands is "clarity". The argument for this is that it corresponds to clear associations with the brand in the consumer's mind.

If you use promotional products to continuously demonstrate the desired emotions over a long period of time, you can achieve a certain effect. This will lead to the brand becoming more intuitively and emotionally understandable, which will increase the chance of being chosen by consumers.

So, based on the explanations of specialists at Kantar, marketers work to create strong emotional connections with consumers, taking into account the needs and common values of the audience.

Based on the above, we can conclude that for a product to belong to the category of brands with a stable position, it is necessary to take into account the functional, emotional, and identification needs of potential consumers.

The company's database includes over 8,500 brands. Of this number, 85% of brand positions do not have an effective emotional connection with consumers on a large scale. And for this reason, enterprises must join a group of brand enterprises of the same level. All this contributes to the fact that trading enterprises are forced to compete only on price.

Kantar surveyed a sample of grocery supermarkets, products (everyday goods). The main goal of this study was to demonstrate which brands have not lost their appeal during the period of martial law in Ukraine.

We conducted a study of well-known brands. As a conclusion, we can note that the strength of a brand in the store category is influenced by the following components: visibility (47%), relevance (38%), and distinction (15%).

For top-tier stores, there is a factor that provides the greatest visibility. This is location. This factor not only demonstrates a physical point on the map, but also indicates the presence of a certain number of sales objects.

As for significance, here we must first talk about emotions in their general sense. This is a set of impressions about a retail establishment, the quality of service, and the convenience of visiting.

The third component, distinctiveness, is determined by the image of the trading enterprise. It is known that when we talk about brand strength, we are primarily talking about predisposition – a predisposition to a certain brand and a desire to buy it.

At present, it can be noted that the leader of the economy category enterprises is ATB-market. Now it is he who has the greatest brand power. Marketers studied the question: why do Ukrainians choose ATB? It is on the example of this market that it is clear that ATB stands out due to its visibility and significance in the economy market category. The most important elements of positioning, the strength of the brand is why Ukrainians choose it. The main role is played by location and prices.

In addition to the above, there are factors that are still worth working on. First of all, this is the assortment, service, social responsibility, – noted by marketing specialists of the Kantar company [12].

It is important to note that in martial law, consumers are more focused on essential goods (food, medicines, hygiene products, self-powered devices, etc.). The profitability of such goods is usually minimal, and the demand is stable. The key role of the company's assortment policy for consumer goods and essential goods is to constantly monitor the availability of a sufficient number of goods at a reasonable price. This task can also become a challenge in the event of disruption of logistics chains or interruptions in the supply of goods. RecommendedPay attention to the capabilities of local suppliers and manufacturers to minimize the risks associated with international logistics. By localizing the supply of goods, it is possible to achieve a reduction in logistics costs and stability of supplies.

Crisis conditions can limit the financial resources of the organization, so it is important to rationally approach the formation of the product range to avoid a surplus of goods or its shortage. Entrepreneurs need to be ready to quickly adapt the range in response to changes. For this purpose, it is recommended to use information technologies that help to better understand consumer needs and forecast demand.

The current situation in the country requires a special approach to product policy. It is precisely through cost reduction and optimization of the logistics chain that profitability is ensured. One of the effective marketing strategies is the sale of related products in order to increase sales volumes. Related products usually complement the main products, increase their

value in the eyes of consumers or satisfy additional customer needs. Given this, it is necessary to qualitatively harmonize the assortment and inform customers about the availability of goods, changes in the assortment and terms of sale.

On the other hand, the low level of competitiveness of Ukrainian enterprises' products is one of the main causes of the crisis phenomena currently observed in the economy, and on the other hand, it directly affects the formation of the enterprise's product portfolio.

Despite the military actions, it cannot be said that competition in the market exists, there is a rivalry between commodity producers for more favorable conditions for production and sale of products, for obtaining maximum profit and other advantages. This competition is carried out by various methods and can appear in various forms. Therefore, there is a need to constantly search for new ways to increase the competitiveness of the enterprise, optimize its product policy [7].

At the stage of implementing the company's product policy, changing market conditions require continuous monitoring, conducting marketing research and analysis. To most fully satisfy the demand of potential consumers, reduce costs and increase asset turnover, trading enterprises need to manage the assortment, relying on the current results of assessing the competitiveness of goods.

Among the common methods for analyzing the assortment policy of an enterprise, the following should be distinguished: ABC and XYZ analysis methods, the Dibb Simkin method, the BCG matrix (classical, modified, adapted). Each of the methods has its own advantages and disadvantages, so it is recommended to be guided by the results of several analysis methods.

General plan for controlling the company's product policy:

1. Determine the actually achieved indicators (sales volumes, number of customers, market share, etc.);
2. Compare actual indicators with planned ones;
3. Summarize the implementation of product policy;
4. Conduct an analysis of identified deviations in indicators and generate a report;
5. Develop a plan of measures and actions aimed at improving indicators, and appoint those responsible for their implementation.

Conclusion

Martial law in the country creates a special importance of innovative methods of increasing competitiveness for trading enterprises. A successfully formed product policy gives the enterprise significant advantages over competitors, opens up opportunities for gaining a larger market share and the prospect of expanding sales markets, will ensure the formation of the image of a dynamic, consumer-oriented organization. Due to the optimization of the product range and the process of its renewal, sales will increase, the effectiveness of control will increase, thereby giving the company the opportunity to quickly respond to market changes.

Abstract

In the conditions of martial law, enterprises face numerous challenges that require optimization and adaptation of their product and assortment policy. The article is devoted to the study of strategies and approaches to the optimization of the assortment and product offer of enterprises during the crisis. The content of the assortment policy and product policy in the context of the trade situation is determined. Definitions of product policy and assortment policy are compared, the features of each of them are revealed. The structure, stages and aspects of the formation of the company's marketing product policy were studied. The article also considers theoretical and methodological approaches to the formation and management of assortment policy based on the life cycle of the product, which allows effective management of the assortment in accordance with the stages of product development. Decisions made by trading enterprises within the framework of trade policy and peculiarities in the construction of commodity policy in this type of organization are considered.

Special attention is paid to the methods of optimization of stocks and management of resources to ensure the competitiveness of the enterprise in the conditions of martial law in the country. The article emphasizes the importance of flexibility and rapid adaptability of enterprises to changing market conditions and the role of innovative technologies in this process. Attention is drawn to the importance of conducting consumption analysis, forecasting trends and assessing product competitiveness, including determining the market positions of the organization during the rapid transformation of the market and changes in consumer habits.

The results of the analysis of changes in consumer demand caused by crisis conditions are highlighted. The methods of confronting the difficulties faced by the enterprises of Ukraine operating at the present time are considered. On the basis of the conducted research, recommendations were developed for the formation of an effective product and assortment policy, which allows enterprises not only to survive, but also to maintain competitiveness during martial law. The urgent need for further scientific research is emphasized.

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